

ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TERRITORIES AND THE FORMATION OF A "GREEN ECONOMY"

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Abstract. *This thesis provides feedback on the directions of economic-social development of territories, ensuring sustainable economic growth of territories, the formation, development of a "green" economy, the world experience of the transition to a "green" economy, the strategy of the transition to a "green" economy.*

Global politics have mostly focused on managing the development trend in the shift to a "green" economy. The difficulties in implementing the "green" economy in the Republic of Azerbaijan are discussed in the essay, along with the contemporary theoretical underpinnings of both the "green" economy and economic development.

A consequence of the expansion of the world economy is environmental degradation. Social development, environmental protection, economic expansion, and inclusive development for everyone are integrated in a green economy. This type of economic development is novel. One of the many challenges countries face as they green economy is a lack of financing and technology. While developing countries are aware of the need for a green transition, their economies are often built on the extraction, processing. This fact makes it difficult for these countries to meet the requirements of modern carbon emissions

Keywords: *"Green" Economy, concept of sustainable development, development of territories, trend of "green" economy, energy resources and efficiency.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the main goals of the sustainable economic development of the country is not only to bring nature and its wealth to today's generation, but also to the next generation in full preservation. Full achievement of sustainable economic growth is gaining importance day by day. Therefore, the implementation of measures for the socio-economic development of territories and the transition to a "green" economy is now gaining importance.

The effective functioning of the world's countries and their economies, the effectiveness of the economic activities of the regions are closely linked to the problems of sustainable socio-economic development of countries and their territories using the principles of a "green" economy in our present day.

Green economy refers to an economy with a high standard of living of the population, with careful and rational use of Natural Resources in the interests of current and future generations and in accordance with the international environmental obligations of the country[1].

The development of production in the country on the principles of the green economy is considered a new direction. In Uzbekistan, much attention began to be paid to this direction after 2017. Legal and regulatory framework is also being formed in this direction. In particular, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the strategy of Action for the further

development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated February 7, 2017 PD-4947 and “on the program of measures for the further development of renewable energy, the development of economic networks and energy efficiency in the social sphere” dated May 26, 2017 PD 3012 in 2017-2021, PD-5863 of October 30, 2019, decree “on approval of the concept of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period up to 2030”, PD-4477 of October 5, 2019, is instrumental in establishing the main directions aimed at the development of this “green “economy. These documents state that the transition to a green economy is one of the strategic directions of the economy of Uzbekistan.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev's decree PD-60 of January 28, 2022 on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, PD-4702 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the rating system of socio-economic development of Regions, dated January 8, 2019, PD-4102 of the Republic of Uzbekistan on further measures to improve the activities of sectors for the complex socio-economic development, In the decisions of PD-3182 of August 8, 2017 “on priority measures to ensure the rapid socio-economic development of Regions”, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 23, 2021 “measures to introduce a system for assessing the effectiveness of sector activities in the complex socio-economic development of Regions”, based on the tasks set out in, a number of measures on the issues of socio-economic complex development of the regions are established, which are being implemented in stages.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The foundations of green economics go back to classical economic theory. Classical period economists Ricardo, Maltus and Mill developed important facts about “growth boundaries”. Maltus relied on the phenomenon of scarcity of the growth threshold, and, taking the usable area as permanent, stressed the need to limit population growth. Ricardo relied on his explanations for the decline in fertility due to the homogeneity of the soil. Ricardo believes that due to the fact that the growing population is forced to use areas with low productivity, after a certain period of time, the standard of living decreases and population growth stops. Mill, on the other hand, has a more optimistic view of "steady state" than Ricardo, believing that a better distribution of wealth can be achieved as a result of individual reason and thrift.

Classical economists theorize that economics is automatically balanced by the invisible hand, and combined with their assumptions and approaches that natural resources are not depleted prioritize economic growth and development while the use of Natural Resources and environmental pollution move to second place. According to Cato, green economics differs from the dominant economic paradigm practiced by politicians and taught at universities in three main ways: first, it is related to social justice. For the green economist, equality and Justice outweigh efficiency.

Many economists who have studied Development Economics in the past and contributed to the development of the green economy are trying to create an international economy in which all people of the world are equal. Secondly, the green economy originated from environmental advocates and green politicians. They try to build a stable economy in practice, and not an abstract theory. Thirdly, the green economy was not yet an area of academic education in universities. In the academic environment and the university itself, debate has become a captive of the globalizing economic system (Cato, 2009, p.5).

Adam Smith, known as the father of classical economics, believes that the biggest obstacle to economic development is the government trying to limit private entrepreneurship. We will consider this concept in the motto of the classical economy “let them pass, let them rest” (*laissez faire, laissez passer*). This idea assumes that within the framework of the activities of the market economy, all types of problems must be solved, and authoritarian interventions such as prohibitions and regulation will reduce well-being.

In the economic history of the Liberal economy, it is seen to interfere in market activities in some areas. Some of these interventions are manifested as benefits and subsidies applied to move the market to any desired business. With the transition to a green economy, it is generally accepted that the stability of economic development increases and the values left to future generations provide a sufficient level of well-being for both them and the generations that follow them. Hoar believes that the enterprise and the market should be reorganized within the framework of the green economy. While the role of the private sector is important in the transition to a green economy, government regulation is also important, especially for large private sectors. Regulatory mechanisms covering atmospheric pollution and emissions, water pollution, environmental taxes and fines are important tools of the green economy (Hor, 2011, p.28). But the real problem arises when it comes to securing the funds that will be spent on the development of the rules necessary for the green economy. The manufacturer does not want to raise high costs, nor does the consumer want to face high prices. In this context, “should it be or should it not be?” the intervention of the state, which will be discussed, is necessary.

Since the 1970s, sustainability has been a major topic of discussion on the solution of environmental problems, and has gained a prominent place in economic theory (Harborth, 1991).

Since the early 1990s, climate change, global warming, and environmental issues have been frequently brought to the agenda by international organizations. Climate change poses a serious threat to poverty reduction and threatens countries' efforts to achieve economic development. Climate change resulting from sustainable production and consumption has a negative impact on the agricultural and agricultural development sectors. And in the end, it generates negative fluctuations in the economy as a result of loss of income, health and productivity. Climate change threatens the living conditions of the community and the chances of survival of the community or species remain uncertain. The main economic considerations are limited to short-term concerns. However, generational equality and future generation rights are phenomena that require a long-term economic perspective. The green economy supports the abandonment of Natural Resources and a habitable planet in order to anticipate humanity and nature, prevent negative impacts, and meet the needs of each generation (Kenneth & Heinemann, 2006, p.2006). 70).

In the classic model, which reflects the economic outlook of current modern societies, an increase in the purchasing power of individuals is achieved by increasing the Gross National Product (GDP). It is based on unlimited production and consumption. According to this view, the goal of economic development is to increase the standard of living of people by providing more goods and services to the growing population. The rapid and unplanned consumption of resources in this endless production, aimed at increasing the standard of living of humanity, prevents the investments necessary for the development of future generations (Tiras, 2012).

The United Nations expects international cooperation and investment to concentrate in the following areas to implement the Global Green order proposed by the organization. These areas are:

- * Investments aimed at reducing the amount of CO₂ due to primary energy consumption through the construction of green buildings for sustainable urbanization, the efficient and efficient use of energy in all old and new buildings

- Renewable energy sectors such as wind, solar, geothermal and biomass, waste recycling and its use.

- * Hybrid and alternative fuel vehicles, high-speed rail systems, public transport and marine transport system.

- * Investments to promote, protect and ensure sustainability of the soil, freshwater resources, forests and fishing sectors that make up the infrastructure of our land.

- Implementation of all necessary measures and investments for Sustainable Agriculture, which prioritizes organic agriculture.

Today, the most important sectors of the green economy are renewable energy sources, green construction and infrastructure, and organic agricultural sectors. The constant promotion and investment for the development of these sectors is a priority issue on the agenda of developed countries. The money transferred to the economy through these benefits and investments will transform unsustainable business opportunities for the private sectors. Jobs created within this framework are called “green jobs”.

The formation of a “green” economy and its sustainable development are considered one of the top priorities both on a global scale and for Uzbekistan. Because the concept of sustainable development is an important resource for the future of humanity, it is reflected in the decisions and documents of the UN. The formation and development of a “green” economy is today the economic and environmental basis of sustainable development. To overcome today's unstable trends, in 2015, specific UN criteria for the development of 17 “green” economies for the period up to 2030 were developed.

In the world experience of the transition to a “green” economy, the following general trends in the development of a “green” economy can be seen:

- By 2050, the planet's population will reach 9 billion;
- global climate change occurs;
- the price of energy resources, raw materials, food products increases by 40-50%, and various crises arise;
- the environment is polluted, 11 million hectares of forests are cut down per year, ecosystems are disrupted, the natural fertility of the soil decreases;
- ecological refugees arise;
- drinking water volume decreases by 60-70 %;
- In 2030, 47% of the planet's population suffers from a lack of drinking water;
- the globe is filled with toxic waste and “buried” [2].

From the above trends, the problem of natural changes occurring on Earth, environmental problems, changes in natural climatic conditions, the gradual depletion of Natural Resources, a decrease in natural productivity, incomplete satisfaction of the food needs of the population, the occurrence of hunger, the loss of drinking water sources, the problem of lack of drinking water, which is still a problem,, we see that the animal world is being exterminated.

In order to develop the economy in our country as well as to maintain balance in the Republic of Uzbekistan on a number of issues such as supply and demand, employment and unemployment, sustainable development of Regions and so on, our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev's decree on PD-60 “new Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026” was adopted. The III direction of this decree was called “rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates” and included the following goals:

continuous supply of electricity to the economy, as well as active introduction of green economy technologies to all sectors, increase the energy efficiency of the economy by 20%.

increase the territorial economy by 1.4 — 1.6 times through the proportional development of territories.

development of the engineering and communication and social infrastructure system of the regions and the service and service sectors[3].

As can be seen from the above, in order to ensure sustainable economic growth in the country, it is necessary to develop territories in a balanced way, ensure the penetration of investment into the country, form, develop the “green economy” in the country, and use the technologies of the “green economy” in all sectors and sectors. It is also dared to develop a plan of measures in advance and apply them in practice to eliminate all the natural, economic, social and similar problems that await us in front of us, and, alternatively, countries will introduce a “green economy” and take advantage of all its achievements.

RESULTS

Green jobs are also defined as well-paid and career jobs that directly contribute to the protection or improvement of Environmental Quality. Green collar jobs are jobs between low skill levels and high skilled entry levels, with high pay and providing opportunities for promotion in terms of Skill Development and pay. Green jobs should also be a good job that includes safe working conditions and workers' rights, including the right to organize trade unions. This type of Labor, also known as decent labor, is defined as decent, rational and effective labor opportunities for women and men with freedom, equality and security conditions. Suitable labor must ensure the opportunities and income that people dream of throughout their labor activities, recognition, family stability, personal development, justice and gender equality.

Positive and negative effects of employment

Environmental Protection and improvement regulations can create new jobs or protect existing ones. Environmental protection programs, on the contrary, can lead to the closure of factories. Environmental protection programs can lead to price increases that reduce demand, production, and employment. This can also lead to companies transferring new production capacities to foreign countries where pollution control regulations apply more freely. Direct and indirect effects of employment. Direct employment effects are the first stage effects of demand, production and employment resulting from increased environmental protection costs. Indirect employment effects are second and third stage effects that occur when other costs not related to environmental protection are included in Environmental Protection costs. The indirect effect of work occurs as follows:

Search and service requirement caused by environmental costs.

Multiplier effect, which occurs as a result of an increase in wages as a result of an increase in demand and employment.

Relative salary and price effect.

Shift effects that occur when pollution-controlling investments replace regular investments.

Effects of short- and long-term employment

Many direct effects, such as increased demand, occur relatively quickly. Indirect effects take longer to affect the economy. For example, the shift of capital to pollution sites creates a negative impact of employment in the long run.

Effects of temporary and stable employment

When measuring the impact on employment, it is important to determine which of them are temporary and which are stable (the term permanent is not preferred here, since it is difficult to predict the actual duration of work).

Full-time and part-time employment effects

The impact of environmental activities on employment can include part-time and full-time work. Two different indicators are useful for this differentiation. First, all jobs created (complete and incomplete) are expressed in full-time equivalents to reflect the total amount of jobs. Secondly, from the point of view of the fight against unemployment, it is enough to determine the number of jobs created.

Unlike the traditional economy, which focuses primarily on expanding “output,” i.e., gross domestic product (GDP) or gross national income (GNI), the green economy promotes a triple bottom line of sustaining and advancing economic, environmental and social well-being. A green economy can also serve as a powerful vehicle to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1]; because of the transversal nature of the SDGs [2] green economy measures can be found in targets across many goals, as illustrated below.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Contribution of the Green Economy to achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals

Picture 1 Sustainable Development Goals

CONCLUSION

At the same time, the "green economy" promotes territorial development, the development of regions, further increasing economic potential through the creation of new jobs in the sectors of the "green economy".

Given that the transition to a "green economy" reduces climate change, the disappearance of minerals and the risk of global problems such as shortage of drinking water resources, focusing on World Development as a whole, its common feature is manifested, that is, when today's world civilization accumulates strength, at the peak of its power, all countries of the world do not choose an, in the context of today's globalization, we can say that the entire planet also faces a gradual decline and a threat of complete extinction.

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